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Jainism : Way of Peace

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Jainism is one of the oldest living religions of India. In ancient times Jainism was called *Śramaṇadharmā*. Antiquity of Jainism goes back to Pre-historic period of Indian culture. We find references of *Vrātya* and *Arhata*s in *Ṛigveda* and *Atharvaveda*, the oldest texts of Indian literature. They were also known as *śramaṇas* in *Upaniṣadic* period. We find mention of some *Jaina Tīrthaṅkara* such as *Ṛṣabhadeva*, *Ajitanātha* and *Ariṣṭanemi* in them. It is a certain proof that Jainism in its oldest form as *vrātya* tradition was prevalent at the time of the composition of the *Vedas* hence its antiquity goes back to pre-vedic period. Secondly in *Mohen-jo-daro* and *Harappa* some seals of meditating yogis have been found which show that the tradition of performing meditation and yoga was prevalent much earlier in the Indian culture. In earlier days, present Jainism was known as a *Vrātya-Dharma*, *Ārhat-dharma* and *Nirgrantha-Dharma*. Many evidences are found also in the vedic purāṇas that our nation's name Bharat Barsh came from the first jain *Tīrthaṅkara Ṛṣabhadeva*'s elder son named *Bharata*. After *Ṛṣabhadeva* there were twenty three *Tīrthaṅkara*s profounded the Jainism and the last twenty fourth *Tīrthaṅkara* Lord Mahāvīra spread Jainism in all over India.

Lord Mahāvīra regarded the individual and his social responsibilities as the key to the progress of both the individual and the society. The teachings of Lord Mahāvīra are as useful and fresh and they were 2600 years age. He always advised his disciples to discover the truth after taking into account all aspects and giving them

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due weight. This broadens one's outlook and trains the mind to accommodate the feelings and the way of life of other faiths and communities. Lord Mahāvīra was a towering personality who has left a lasting impact in the form of his teachings for the spiritual advancement of personality who has left a lasting impact in the form of his teachings for the spiritual advancement of the individual protection and conservation of all forms of life, and a rational, just, peaceful and secular social order.

Today I would like to discuss only two main theory of Mahāvīra which is very necessary for world peace and prosperity. That is *Ahimsā* (Non-Violence) and *Anekānta* (non-absolutism).

Theory of Non-Violence

The philosophy of non violence is a living practice. More than refraining from violence, it is a deep reverence for all life. It starts by cultivating a genuine respect for one self; one's consciousness or life force, and for each of its supportive elements the body, mind and emotions. We come to realize that our life force is precious and that we are here to respect and innate wisdom. It is a process of taking care of both our inner being and the material envelope in which it dwells. Like a mother nurturing the development of her child, we do what is healthful and helpful for our spiritual growth. When a well known Sanskrit scholar Jain *Ācārya* Samantabhadra 4th A.D.) announces that in this world *Ahimsā* of living being is equivalent to Brahma, the metaphysical reality, he is propounding *Ahimsā* as the highest social value-

*Ahimsā bhutānām jagati viditam brahma paramam*¹

(अहिंसाभूतानां जगति विदितं ब्रह्मपरमं)

Co-existence and Parasparopagraho Jivānam

Everybody should know the famous Jain emblem, which contained at its base the following *sūtra*:

Parasparopagraho jivānam.² (परस्परपग्रहो जीवानाम्)

This is an important aphorism from the first Sanskrit book in the Jain tradition called *Tattvārthasūtra* by Ācārya Umāswāmi. It means that living beings (*jīvas*) are mutually related through favour and obligation, i.e. beneficence. The industrialist pays wages to the labourer and the latter acts in a manner likely to benefit the former and to safeguard his interests. Likewise, the teacher imparts knowledge to the pupil and makes his go through a sacred ceremony. The latter moulds himself according to the teacher and respectfully obeys his directions. Both are examples of mutual beneficence. Life's formula is not conflict, for conflict denotes helplessness and is not an independent trait. On the other hand mutual beneficence is an independent trait. While treating life as conflict that compels man to take the course of violence, mutual beneficence takes him on the road to non-violence.

Definition of Non-violence (*Ahimsā*)

In Jainism, nonviolence is not limited to refraining from mental, verbal and physical injury to human beings. It encompasses abstaining from injury to all living beings- all animals and plants. The ancient Jain scripture, *Ācārāṅga sūtra* presents a highly sophisticated discussion on nonviolence. It states that one should not cause injury to any living being, including the tiniest creatures and plants. All life depends on nature for survival. Thus disturbing the ecological balance by wasting nature resources and polluting water and air also constitutes violence. In *Ācārāṅga* he says, *savve pāṇā ṇa haṁtavvā, ṇa ajjāvetavva, ṇa ajjāvetavvā, ṇa parighettavvā, ṇa paritāveyavvā, ṇa uddveyavvā*.³ (सव्वे पाणा ण हंतव्वा, ण अज्जावेतव्वा, ण परिशेतव्वा, ण परित्तावेयव्वा, ण उद्दवेयव्वा।)

Lord Mahāvīra made a simple yet profound statement, based on the absorption of the non-violence into the fabric of his consciousness. He realized--

Jaha te na piyam dukham, Janiye emeva savvajivanam.

जह ते न पिअम दुक्खं, जाणिए एमेव सव्वजीवाणं।

Savvayaramauvautto, Attovammena kunasu dayama.⁵

सव्वायरमुवउत्तो, अत्तोवम्मेण कुणसु दयं।।

Tumam si nama sa veva, Jama hantavvama ti mannasi.

नाम सच्चेव, जं हंतव्वं ति मन्नसि,

Tumam si nama sa ceva, Jama hantavvama to mannasi.⁶

तुमंसि नाम सच्चेव, जं अज्जावेयव्वं ति मन्नसि,

Jain literature explains not only general way of life with *Ahimsā* but spiritual too. The deep theory of Lord Mahāvīra's spiritual non-violence has been also explained in this text and this is the original theory of *ahimsā* as explained by Lord Mahāvīra.

One of the distinctive marks of Jainism has been its long tradition of nonviolence. Living as we do in an era of unparalleled violence, this feature of the Jaina ethics can stimulate contemporary interest for finding solutions to our global problems.

Thus Jaina ethic trains good dutiful and morally conscious citizens who can help in maintaining world peace. If ethical code is followed, the heavy work of a state is facilitated and crores of rupees can be saved for other welfare activities. Jainism asks us to subdue our passions and always act with mindfulness and caution. The negligence of these men are let loose with the result that the demon of destruction stalks this land of human beings? By stressing on pure, simple and honest household life, Jainism paves the way for world peace.

It is an admitted fact these days that vegetarian diet is the first step towards world peace. Jainism has been preaching and practicing vegetarianism from the hoary past. Jaina sages were the first to propagate vegetarian diet.

Besides these Jaina ascetics lead life of purity, celibacy, service and perfect austerity. They have nothing to claim of their own and all the living beings are their friends par excellence. Their high moral

and pure character can appeal to the masses a great deal. People of various religions and different countries should unite at this crucial juncture of world history and carry on ceaseless propaganda to save the humanity from its extinction. It is fundamentally essential that we try our best to revitalize religious and moral principles common to all the religious sects of the world. If pacifists all over the world stand up and unite together with an iron will to ensure peace and harmony, heaven can be established without fail on this very earth. Religious and moral disarmament need precede physical one. Jainism expects every individual to inculcate in him/her amity towards all beings, serene joy towards the good, compassion for the miserable and detachment towards the opponent.

Anekāntavāda (non-absolutism)

Lord Mahāvīra gave the theory of *Anekāntavāda*, that is many-sidedness. *Anekānta* encourages interpersonal and communal harmony by promoting tolerance in the community. The same principle of tolerance can be extended to intellectual, social, religious and other fields of activities. Tolerance and enunciated by *Anekānta*, will end all inter-caste strife and communal violence. *Anekānta* is thus the pillar of religious and social harmony and the sheet anchor of secularism. *Anekānta* ensures peaceful co-existence of all shades of philosophical and religious opinions, paths as well as their followers. They pointed to a new era of hope and promise for the masses delivering social equality, Peace, empowerment of women, non-violence, tolerance and social justice.

***Anekāntavāda* and Co-existence**

The *Anekāntavāda* believes in co-existence. The principle of co-existence is as much practical as it is philosophical. Though the terms system, individual, taste and viewpoint have different denotations even implying inherent opposition, the principle of co-existence applies to them too. Democracy and dictatorship, capitalism and communism

are ideologically different political systems. But even they are no exception to co-existence. ‘You or me’ not ‘you and me’ is an instance of absolutism by which the problem gets compounded. The holiness of the world of religion has been destroyed by the view: “Only those have the right to survive who follow my religion, all the rest should be extirpated,” The main strengths of religion are non-violence, friendliness and fraternity. The absolutism view has changed nonviolence into violence, friendliness into hostility and fraternity into animosity. Co-existence implies tolerance and freedom of thought. Both tolerance and freedom of thought are meaningless if we try to enforce our likes, ideas, lifestyle and principles on others.

Nature has infinite variety, lifestyle which lends it splendor, Beauty will lose all its charms and meaning if all plants, trees and flowers look alike. The combined principle of *satyam* (truth), *Śivam* (benefaction), *sundaram* (beauty) inheres in the principle of unity in diversity and diversity in unity. It is only the above harmony which forms the basis of co-existence.

***Anekāntavāda* and Tolerance**

The dictionary meaning of ‘Tolerance’ exposes the negative aspect of acceptance in a dominant manner. It tolerance is taken to mean ‘ability or capacity to tolerate’, it well point to toleration out of compulsion, out of helplessness or out of dire need of survival. For example, tolerating the baddies in the classroom or undisciplined behavior of even the notorious people in the society. It may even indicate the attitude of treating the other person with condemnation or the attitude of superiority complex and treating other as inferior, e.g. rich people tolerating weak, underdeveloped countries etc. Hence, it cannot be regarded as the view that holds the capacity of ‘tolerate’ the other views, but rather it can correctly be described as that view which treats all other views, including itself, with equanimity. In holding such temper of equanimity, *Anekāntavāda* demands surrender of undue pride in one’s own existence and supremacy and tend to develop

humility and senses of respect towards other perspectives. In the present circumstances of communal disturbances and religious tensions everywhere, *Anekāntavāda* can be applied as a paradigm to solve these battles. It can be convinced to the classes and masses that all religions are different pathways to the same goal, and that there is no room for superiority or inferiority of any religion. All religious faiths are equally respectable. The theory can be applied to many spheres of life where there are battles arising out of misunderstanding. And it can be well understood that it is the theory advocating equanimity among and respect towards all the possible alternative, rather than the ability to 'tolerate'. Similarly in our democratic form of government, doctrine of *Anekāntavāda* is very important for both the ruling and opposition parties to accept existence of each as real and learn to live with each other in a logical and peaceful manner.

Conclusion

We live in a spendthrift universe of continuous giving. Everywhere the sun is radiating its warmth and light. The very breath of life is carried to us upon the air and wind. Clouds and oceans follow the same law to shower upon us their precious waters. Earth cultivates all manner of vegetation from which grain and fruit sprout forth. Our bodies are made of vegetation from which grain and fruit sprout forth. Our bodies are made of all these gifts. What are we giving back to this all providing universe? Where there is abundance in our lives, are we sharing it or taking more than our share? Though we are receiving of its bounty, are we allowing ignorance, fear, apathy, or ego to blind us to the generous heart on or earth? Are we saturating the atmosphere, the seas, and with deadly waste pollutant? How long will Mother Nature continue to bear with this ingratitude of ours? When blood soaks the land, we label it enemy blood or friend blood, locking up or letting loose our emotions accordingly. In the same way, when the throats of helpless creatures are cut, human minds categorize, rationalize, and explain, cutting hearts off from natural compassion. Where has our human capacity for feeling and empathy gone?

Today we have conquered distances. We are no longer living as isolated individuals. Our activities and thinking now encompass not only the country we belong to, but the whole world. This is an important development. However, let us not forget the truth that the center of all consciousness lays within the individual, no matter whether it is individual consciousness or collective consciousness. Therefore, the dream of world peace cannot be realized without refining the individual consciousness. The individual is relegated to the secondary position as soon as peace becomes an organizational matter or a matter related to management. Now, what characterizes good organization or management is complete control. But such control is subversive of peace. Therefore, sooner or later, one will have to awaken social consciousness in individuals to ensure world peace. This social consciousness is in traditional terms consciousness of equity.

In our natural state, our soul is nothing but love, energy, peace and bliss. Gradually we glide to peak of realization and joy, exclaiming, "I am my cells with awareness!" and before buying or using any product, we ask "by my action, am I causing any living being to pay a price in pain? Directly or indirectly, am I causing a life to be lost?" In this way, the trials of life become instrumental for our growth, and we come closer to our goal, i.e. self realization. As we tune an instrument using right key for better results, we must tune ourselves in right direction all life. By minimizing attachment, violence and sadistic approach, we enjoy life with a light heart enjoying calm of mind.

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